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How to Find Accurate Terrain and Canopy Height GEDI Footprints in Temperate Forests and Grasslands?

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Key Points:

- Terrain is crucial for estimates of canopy height, however only 20%–30% of footprints have an absolute error of terrain estimates <3 m
- The quality of terrain and canopy height estimates depends on the interplay of number of modes, sensitivity, land cover, and terrain slope
- Noise and low-quality footprints can be successfully removed using number of modes, sensitivity, quality flag and difference from TanDEM-X

Supporting Information:

Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

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Abstract Filtering approaches on Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) data differ considerably across existing studies and it is yet unclear which method is the most effective. We conducted an in-depth analysis of GEDI's vertical accuracy in mapping terrain and canopy heights across three study sites in temperate forests and grasslands in Spain, California, and New Zealand. We started with unfiltered data (2,081,108 footprints) and describe a workflow for data filtering using Level 2A parameters and for geolocation error mitigation. We found that retaining observations with at least one detected mode eliminates noise more effectively than sensitivity. The accuracy of terrain and canopy height observations depended considerably on the number of modes, beam sensitivity, landcover, and terrain slope. In dense forests, a minimum sensitivity of 0.9 was required, while in areas with sparse vegetation, sensitivity of 0.5 sufficed. Sensitivity greater than 0.9 resulted in an overestimation of canopy height in grasslands, especially on steep slopes, where high sensitivity led to the detection of multiple modes. We suggest excluding observations with more than five modes in grasslands. We found that the most effective strategy for filtering low-quality observations was to combine the quality flag and difference from TanDEM-X, striking an optimal balance between eliminating poor-quality data and preserving a maximum number of high-quality observations. Positional shifts improved the accuracy of GEDI terrain estimates but not of vegetation height estimates. Our findings guide users to an easy way of processing of GEDI footprints, enabling the use of the most accurate data and leading to more reliable applications.

Plain Language Summary The Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) collected terrain and canopy observations using laser altimetry. The quality of terrain and canopy observations is influenced by acquisition conditions and land (cover) characteristics. Consequently, a considerable amount of GEDI observations is discarded as noise, and further filtering is necessary to retain only high-quality observations. Our objective was to assess how environmental and acquisition characteristics influence the accuracy of terrain and canopy height of GEDI observations. Although the main objective of the GEDI mission was to map forests, we also focused on grasslands. GEDI serves not only as an essential source of information on canopy height but also provides accurate terrain observations. Furthermore, it is important to know that GEDI does not overestimate the height of low vegetation as this can result in an overestimation of carbon storage. We distinguished four steps in the GEDI data processing: (a) removal of noise observations, (b) removal of low-quality data, (c) effect of additional acquisition characteristics, and (d) mitigation of geolocation error. We found that the accuracy of terrain and canopy height observations depended considerably on the number of detected modes, beam sensitivity, landcover, and terrain slope.

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1. Introduction

Forests play a key role in biodiversity conservation and regulation of the global carbon cycle (Mo et al., 2023; Pan et al., 2011). It is well recognized that the vertical and horizontal structure of forests, including their height, are important indicators of biodiversity (Cazzolla Gatti et al., 2017; Davies & Asner, 2014) and vegetation structure is, therefore, considered one of the six essential classes of biodiversity variables (Moudry et al., 2023; Skidmore et al., 2021). Furthermore, vegetation structure is directly linked to the above-ground biomass and primary productivity, both being critical components of carbon stock and flux (Fisher et al., 2019). Vegetation structure measurements are, therefore, essential for creating climate action plans, the preparation of which is underway in many countries (Grassi et al., 2017; Hoover & Smith, 2021).

However, until recently, we lacked comprehensive global data on the spatial patterns of forest structure and available estimates remained uncertain due to data limitations and availability (Herold et al., 2019). This has changed with the two recent space-based laser altimetry missions launched in 2018 that have mapped the forest structure with unprecedented accuracy on a global scale (Dubayah et al., 2022; Neuenschwander & Pitts, 2019). These two missions, GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation) and ICESat-2 (Ice, Cloud, and Land Elevation Satellite-2), provide direct measurements of the terrain and canopy heights, and, therefore, considerably improve our ability to monitor forests globally (Dubayah et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021; Markus et al., 2017). The GEDI mission specifically aims to measure forest structure and biomass in tropical and temperate regions. It is the first spaceborne lidar mission specifically designed for such a purpose (Dubayah et al., 2020). The GEDI data have been, for example, used to assess the role of forest structure in biodiversity patterns (Marselis et al., 2022; Torresani et al., 2023), to improve models of animal-environment relationships (Smith et al., 2022), or to assess the effectiveness of protected areas in conserving vegetation structure and carbon stocks (Ceccherini et al., 2023; Liang et al., 2023).

The GEDI instrument was mounted on the International Space Station (ISS) and collected data between April 2019 and March 2023. GEDI fired 16 billion laser pulses at the Earth's surface each year. Compared to ICESat-2, it had a higher sampling density in temperate and tropical forests, but its spatial coverage was limited to the latitude range of 51.6°S–51.6°N (ISS inclination angle). GEDI has a 25 m diameter footprint, which is recommended for measuring canopy height using spaceborne lidar for biodiversity and habitat science (Bergen et al., 2009). The location of each GEDI footprint is computed using the observed range combined with the instrument pointing and position (derived from star tracker and GPS sensors; Beck et al., 2021). The horizontal geolocation error of GEDI footprints is 10 ± 2 m (V002) and is expected to improve in upcoming data versions (Beck et al., 2021). An empirical vertical accuracy of GEDI canopy height estimates is approximately 2–3 m (Hakkenberg, Tang, et al., 2023), which more or less meets the recommended vertical accuracy for measuring canopy height using spaceborne lidar (Bergen et al., 2009). Such accuracy, however, assumes ideal measurement conditions, which are rarely met; the actual accuracy is, therefore, degraded due to environmental conditions during the data acquisition (e.g., Dorado-Roda et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2021). GEDI's lasers operate at a 1,064 nm wavelength (near-infrared), thus unable to penetrate dense cloud cover (Dubayah et al., 2020). Therefore, only approximately 50% of pulses were expected to provide a useful signal, while the remaining 50% were expected to be lost or degraded (Dubayah et al., 2020; eoPortal, 2016). Further, degraded accuracy may have resulted from the interaction of the laser with the Earth's atmosphere, solar background noise, and/or processes (algorithms) used to determine the height metrics (Adam et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021; Quiros et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022).

Due to the low accuracy of some of the GEDI observations, they must be filtered before being used to estimate terrain or vegetation structure. Indeed, the selection of accurate GEDI footprints is crucial for the preparation of downstream GEDI data products, such as gridded mean canopy height (Dubayah, Luthcke, et al., 2021) and above-ground biomass density (Kellner et al., 2023), or any other analysis using GEDI data (e.g., Hoffrén et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021). In this work, we focused on GEDI acquisitions over temperate forests. However, it is equally important to tackle the issue of the overestimation of low vegetation (such as grasslands) as this can result in an overestimation of carbon storage. Moreover, such data are important for mapping landcover types (Dwiputra et al., 2023) and the generation of global canopy height maps (i.e., both areas of high and low vegetation are needed to fit the models; Potapov et al., 2021). In addition, GEDI is not only an important source of information on canopy height, but also of accurate terrain observations that are used to validate existing and create

new global digital elevation models (Narin et al., 2024; Narin & Gullu, 2023; Pronk et al., 2023). Therefore, in this study, we focus on both terrain and canopy height in both forests and grasslands.

However, identifying useable (i.e., high-quality) observations can be challenging. To select high-quality data, the GEDI user guide (Beck et al., 2021) recommends the use of power beams only for the description of dense forests, GEDI footprints acquired at night to avoid the negative effects of solar background illumination on waveform quality, and, finally, assessing footprint sensitivity. The easiest way of data filtering lies in the use of the *quality_flag* parameter as suggested by the GEDI user guide (Beck et al., 2021). Many studies using GEDI data use this flag for data filtering (see Figure 1), but it has also been suggested that the flag tends to remove useable footprints (Geremew et al., 2023). In addition, other approaches have been adopted in existing studies, including, for example, comparing the data to some existing global DEMs (e.g., TanDEM-X DEM or SRTM; Lahssini et al., 2022; Urbazaev et al., 2022) or filtering according to the results acquired using six different Algorithm Setting Groups (ASG) and keeping only observations where all these results are similar (e.g., Potapov et al., 2021). Terrain slope is another factor contributing to the canopy height estimation error (Chen, 2010; Wang et al., 2022). It is, therefore, potentially reasonable to keep only footprints located on relatively flat terrain (e.g., Simard et al., 2011). GEDI data filtering, on the one hand, ensures the use of high-quality data, but, on the other hand, considerably reduces the number of available GEDI footprints (Figure 1). For example, in the study by Hoffrén et al. (2023), filtering resulted in the use of only 16% of all footprints available in their study area. Similarly, Cobb et al. (2023) flagged only 14% of footprints as high-quality.

For inexperienced users, it may be difficult to properly apply available filtering approaches and parameters, which can lead to an unnecessary loss of accurate data, or, vice versa, to an inclusion of inaccurate data. In this study, we evaluate three study sites in temperate forests and grasslands in Spain, California, and New Zealand as examples to show how the individual parameters used for filtering (Figure 1) complement each other. We aim (a) to evaluate the usability of the number of detected modes (i.e., of waveform maxima in the return signal) and sensitivity for removal of noise observations, (b) to quantify the success of three filtering methods in preserving accurate measurements and eliminating inaccurate ones (c) to evaluate the effects of acquisition (e.g., degrade flag, beam strength, acquisition time), and environmental (landcover, slope) characteristics on GEDI observations, and (d) to assess the geolocation error of footprints. In contrast to prior studies (Figure 1), we start with unfiltered data and outline the whole process of high-quality data selection.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Study Areas

We selected three study areas in the temperate biome (Olson et al., 2001) in Spain, New Zealand, and California (USA; Figure 2) based on the availability of airborne laser scanning (ALS) data from the period overlapping with the GEDI data acquisition. We used discrete return ALS data as a reference to analyze errors in terrain elevation and maximum vegetation height of GEDI footprints.

2.1.1. Cantabrian Mountain Range (Spain)

The Cantabrian mixed forests are a transitional zone between the Eurosiberian and the Mediterranean regions of Europe. The study area comprises mainly the Principality of Asturias and small parts of Cantabria and Castilla y León (Spain), including the highest areas of the Cantabrian mountains range at the Picos de Europa National Park with elevations ranging from 0 to 2,648 m (Figure 2). It covers an area of almost 400,000 ha. The average annual temperature is 8–14°C, and average rainfall is 900–1,800 mm. The Cantabrian Range is rich in floral diversity and includes a wide range of forest types. The forests are relatively low, with a typical height of 20 m or less (Figure 2). The lowlands are characterized by broadleaf deciduous forests with English oak (*Quercus robur*), European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), sweet chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), and lindens (*Tilia platyphyllos*, *Tilia cordata*). Forests at higher elevations are characterized by deciduous oaks (*Quercus pyrenaica*, *Quercus petraea*) with European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*). Subalpine plant communities, such as low shrubs and grasses, are found above the tree line.

Overview of parameters used for filtering GEDI footprints in existing studies

Study	Number of footprints		Noise filtering		Low-Quality data filtering			Additional filters		
	raw	filtered	Number of modes	Sensitivity	Quality flag	Difference to global DEM	Range between ASG	Degrade flag	Beam coverage/power	Day or night
Temperate forests of Europe, Canada, and Australia										
Ceccherini et al. (2023)	not stated	49.4 M								
Hoffrén et al. (2023)	59 554	9 703								
Schwartz et al. (2023)	526 449	175 511								
Dhargay et al. (2022)	17 075	11 832								
Kacic et al. (2023)	not stated	30 M								
Mandl et al. (2023)	not stated	11 340								
Pourrahmati et al. (2023)	2.3 M	507 892								
Sothe et al. (2022)	not stated	1.2 M								
Turubanova et al. (2023)	not stated	not stated								
Tropical forests of Asia, Africa, and South America										
Cobb et al. (2023)	38 275	5 292								
Dwiputra et al. (2023)	not stated	79 498								
Geremew et al. (2023)	not stated	3 600								
Lahssini et al. (2022)	not stated	3 864								
Oliveira et al. (2023)	not stated	1 200								
Ngo et al. (2023)	3 600	1 166								
Worldwide or US-wide studies covering a broad range of forests										
Liu et al. (2021)	not stated	90 472								
Rishmawi et al. (2021)	254 M	27 M								
Potapov et al. (2021)	not stated	372 M								
Wang et al. (2022)	not stated	146 292								
Urbazaev et al. (2022)	not stated	11.3 M								
Hakkenberg et al. (2023b)	not stated	not stated								
African Savannas										
Li et al. (2023)	not stated	22 813								

Figure 1. Overview of parameters used for filtering GEDI footprints in existing studies. ASG, algorithm setting groups; DEM, digital elevation model. M, millions.

Figure 2. Location of the study areas and distribution of forest canopy height therein. Canopy height retrieved from ALS data.

Table 1
Lidar Data Characteristics

Study area	Area (km ²)	Year	Horizontal datum/Projection	Vertical datum	Point density
Cantabria	4,200	2018–2021	ETRS 1989 UTM Zone 30N	RE-50	1–2 p/m ²
Marlborough	4,900	2020–2021	NZGD 2000 Transverse Mercator	NZVD2016	9 p/m ²
Trinity	2,400	2019–2020	NAD 1983 (2011) UTM zone 10N	NAVD 88	8 p/m ²

2.1.2. Marlborough Richmond Range (New Zealand)

The study area comprises mainly the northern part of the Marlborough region (South Island of New Zealand), including the Mount Richmond Forest Park and the valley of the Wairau river with elevations ranging from 0 to 1,760 m (Figure 2). The average annual temperature is 7–17°C, and the average rainfall is around 650 mm distributed more or less evenly across the year. Mount Richmond Forest park, located north of Wairau river, was established in 1977 and covers an area of almost 166,000 ha. It is a mountainous landscape that consists of relatively unmodified vegetation and pastures. The height of the forests differs between native manuka (*Leptospermum scoparium*) and kanuka (*Leptospermum ericoides*) trees. Manuka can grow up to 10 m in height, whereas kanuka trees reach heights of up to 25 m (Figure 2). The higher stands, up to 45 m in height, include native beech and plantation forests (*Nothofagus spp.*). South of the Wairau river, grassland is the main vegetation cover.

2.1.3. Trinity Alps Wilderness (California)

The Trinity Alps Wilderness is the second largest wilderness area in California, with over 200,000 ha of land (Figure 2). The Trinity Alps are a subrange of the Klamath Mountains and are characterized by rugged subalpine topography with elevations ranging from 600 to 2,750 m. Rainfall varies between 740 and 2,720 mm of precipitation annually. This area is a transitional zone between the Mediterranean climate of the south and the Northwestern coastal climate, resulting in high plant diversity (e.g., with the second highest number of conifer species worldwide). The typical height of the forest is between 20 and 35 m, but in relatively large parts of the study area, the forest height exceeds 45 m (Figure 2). Trinity Alps are covered by mixed conifer forests (*Pinus ponderosa*, *Pinus contorta*, *Pinus lambertiana*, *Pseudotsuga menziesii*, *Abies concolor*, *Calocedrus decurrens*), red fir forests (*Abies magnifica*, *Pinus jeffreyi*, *Pinus monticola*), and subalpine forests (*Pinus balfouriana*, *Pinus albicaulis*, *Tsuga mertensiana*) (Ferlatte, 1974).

2.2. Reference Data

The airborne lidar data for the study areas were collected between 2018 and 2021, with the point cloud densities between 1 and 9 points per m² (Table 1). The ALS data for the Cantabrian Mountain Range were collected as a part of the PNOA (Plan Nacional de Ortofotografía Aérea) project (2nd coverage flights). The project aims to capture three-dimensional information using airborne lidar sensors of the entire territory of Spain (<https://pnoa.ign.es/>). The reported planimetric and altimetric accuracies in terms of root mean square error (RMSE) are 30 and 15 cm, respectively. The ALS data for the Marlborough Richmond Range were collected as a part of an acquisition campaign to obtain the New Zealand National Elevation Model. The point cloud vertical accuracy at the 95% confidence level required for this campaign is 20 cm in non-vegetated terrain (i.e., 95% of observations have vertical error lower than 20 cm, National Elevation Program of New Zealand). The ALS data for the Trinity Alps Wilderness meet the requirements of the 3D Elevation Program (3DEP), which is designed to collect high-quality ALS data for the United States. The absolute vertical accuracies at the 95% confidence level required for 3DEP are 20 and 30 cm in non-vegetated and vegetated terrain, respectively (Stoker & Miller, 2022).

The already classified ALS point clouds were used to generate digital terrain models (DTM) and canopy height models (CHM) at a 2 m spatial resolution. We used points classified as ground to generate DTMs and the highest returns of normalized point clouds in individual cells to generate CHMs (LASools version 230123). Noise points or points above a height threshold (60 m in Cantabria, and Marlborough, and 80 m in Trinity) were considered noise and not used for CHM generation. We used the DTMs as a reference for GEDI terrain validation and the CHMs as a reference for the validation of the GEDI top canopy height, in line with prior studies (e.g., Liu

GEDI L2A - data processing workflow

Figure 3. Processing workflow. All footprints enter the first step (*Noise filtering*), in which GEDI observations containing no useful information are identified. Here, we compared the performance of both criteria (i.e., the Number of modes and Sensitivity) for noise filtering. Subsequently, all observations that failed in at least one of the criteria were removed. The remaining observations progressed into Step 2. In Step 2 (*Low-quality data filtering*), three approaches for low-quality data filtering were employed, compared, and observations identified as low-quality were removed. The remaining observations were used in Step 3, assessing whether acquisition parameters (*Additional filters*) were needed for additional filtering or if all low-quality data were already filtered in the prior steps. Finally, the remaining observations were used in Step 4, assessing and mitigating the geolocation error of observations.

et al., 2021; Quirós et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2022). We used landcover derived from the ESA world cover product at a 10 m resolution for the year 2020 (<https://esa-worldcover.org/en>) to distinguish forests and grasslands.

2.3. GEDI Instrument and Data

The GEDI lidar, multibeam laser altimeter was composed of three full-waveform Nd:YAG lasers, each with a 15.6 ns pulse and 242 Hz pulse repetition rate in the near-infrared region (1,064 nm). Two of these were used at full power (15 mJ/pulse), while the third one was split into two lower-energy coverage beams (4.5 mJ/pulse). The laser pulses were subjected to dithering, which resulted in a total of eight tracks separated by 600 m. Each pulse had a 25 m footprint, and along the track, the footprints were separated by 60 m (Dubayah et al., 2020).

The geolocated waveforms of received energy (i.e., number of photons) as a function of time (GEDI L1B product; Luthcke et al., 2019) are the fundamental observations made by the GEDI instrument. These are further processed to provide products at the footprint level: the L2A (ground elevation, canopy height, and relative height metrics) and L2B (canopy cover, plant area index) data products. This information is subsequently used to produce gridded data sets; the L3 (mean canopy height map and standard deviation of canopy height map), and L4B (gridded above-ground biomass) data sets, at a 1 km² resolution; the best detail that has ever been produced at the near-global extent.

We used version 2 of the GEDI L2A Elevation and Height Metrics product that provides ground elevation and canopy height metrics of individual footprints. The returned waveform is typically multimodal with the lowest mode (*elev_lowestmode*) representing the ground elevation. The accuracy of ground elevation is crucial for the estimation of canopy height metrics, as the ground serves as an elevation baseline for the canopy height estimation (Hofton & Blair, 2019). The GEDI L2A product provides the relative height (RH) metrics representing the height at which a particular quantile of energy (i.e., 1st–100th quantile) was returned, relative to the elevation of the lowest waveform mode representing the ground (Hofton & Blair, 2019). Here, we use RH98 to represent top canopy height as, for example, Milenković et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2023) regarded this as a robust metric less sensitive to noise than RH100. However, others also used RH95 (Zhu et al., 2022) or RH100 (Adam et al., 2020; Quirós et al., 2021).

2.4. Target and Acquisition Characteristics Useable for GEDI Processing

The L2A product includes several parameters that describe the target and acquisition characteristics and inform users about the footprint data usability, such as the number of modes (*num_detectedmodes*), sensitivity (*sensitivity*), quality flag (*quality_flag*), or degrade flag (*degrade_flag*). We integrated these parameters with other data sources (i.e., TanDEM-X DEM, ALS DTM, ESA world cover) outlining the target characteristics (i.e., terrain height, landcover, slope) to identify the causes of bias in terrain and canopy height observations as well as the usability of these characteristics for data filtering. We classified the data processing into four steps (Figure 3): (a)

filtering based on parameters identifying noise observations (number of modes, sensitivity); (b) filtering used to remove observations with low-quality (quality flag, difference to TanDEM-X DEM, low difference among results of the six algorithm setting groups); (c) filtering based on additional parameters potentially affecting observation accuracy (e.g., the degrade flag, laser pulse energy, time of acquisition, and slope); and (d) mitigating geolocation error using a high-resolution DTM.

2.4.1. Noise Filtering

2.4.1.1. Number of Modes

The number of modes is an important parameter used for noise removal. The returned waveform can have a simple shape with only a single mode (similar to the transmitted output pulse), which is typical of bare ground, or it can be multimodal, which is typical for vegetation or rough terrain. Each mode represents a distinct reflecting surface within the laser footprint. The first mode detected above the noise is associated with the top of the canopy, the last one with the terrain (Beck et al., 2021). Waveforms without detected modes (i.e., waveforms consisting only of noise) correspond to poor observations and, as such, are typically removed from analyses (Figure 1).

2.4.1.2. Beam Sensitivity

The beam sensitivity is a signal detection performance metric that represents the maximum canopy cover that the GEDI can penetrate, correctly detecting the ground below (typically, with an estimated 90% probability of correct identification and a 5% chance of a false positive result; Hancock et al., 2019). Beam sensitivity depends on multiple parameters (receiver efficiency, orbital altitude, telescope area, surface reflectivity, atmospheric transmission, background solar illumination, and laser pulse energy) and can be calculated using the lidar equation (Dubayah et al., 2020; Hancock et al., 2021).

To select high-quality data, the GEDI user guide (Beck et al., 2021), among other characteristics, recommends using a sensitivity threshold of 0.9 over land; under certain conditions, it has been, however, suggested that using a higher threshold can be beneficial under certain circumstances (e.g., dense forest). Therefore, only footprints with sensitivities ranging from 0.9 to 1 are considered valid and typically used as a selection criterion for the removal of noise observations (Figure 1). In addition, beam sensitivity is one of the criteria used in the quality flag (see below).

2.4.2. Low-Quality Data Filtering

2.4.2.1. Quality Flag (QF)

To facilitate filtering of the most useful high-quality observations, GEDI provides a quality flag (*quality_flag*). It is recommended only as general guidance by the GEDI user guide (Beck et al., 2021). However, for its simplicity and ease of use, it is the most commonly adopted criterion (Figure 1). The quality flag combines a set of conditions to indicate whether the waveform can be used for further analyses (1: valid waveform, 0: not valid waveform). The criteria for the quality flag include energy, amplitude, sensitivity, real-time surface tracking quality, and the difference from TanDEM-X DEM. The quality flag uses a beam sensitivity threshold of 0.9 as explained above (see Section 2.4.1). Hereafter, we refer to the approach using the quality flag for filtering as QF.

2.4.2.2. TanDEM-X (TDX) Difference

The GEDI L2A product includes the heights of two global digital elevation models (TanDEM-X and SRTM) that can be used for the assessment of the quality of GEDI observations. A large absolute difference between the GEDI ground elevation (*elev_lowestmode*) and elevation from an existing global digital elevation model (TanDEM-X is typically used for this purpose) can indicate erroneous observations. If the absolute difference exceeds a specified threshold, the observation is removed. The adopted thresholds differ among studies and range from 50 m (Urbazaev et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022) to 75 m (Ngo et al., 2023), 100 m (Geremew et al., 2023; Lahssini et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2022), or even 150 m, which is used for the generation of GEDI L3 Gridded Land Surface Metrics (Dubayah, Luthcke, et al., 2021). Here, we tested the thresholds of 50 and 100 m. Hereafter, we refer to this filtering approach as TDX.

2.4.2.3. Algorithm Setting Groups (ASG)

The waveforms are processed using six possible algorithm setting groups to detect the ground and canopy height available in the L2A product. Each algorithm setting group uses a different combination of parameters to accommodate different acquisition scenarios (e.g., daytime, nighttime, low and high energy lowest modes; see Table 5 in Hofton & Blair, 2019). The most appropriate algorithm setting group for individual footprints is indicated in the GEDI (version 2) data set, determined on the basis of the laser return energy, geographic region, and plant functional type (Beck et al., 2021).

We used all six algorithm setting groups to filter out the low-quality observations. A narrow range of ground elevations predicted by the six algorithm setting groups (i.e., the similarity of their results) may indicate high-accuracy observations and can be used for their filtering (e.g., Potapov et al., 2021). Following Potapov et al. (2021), we used the threshold of the maximum difference between all six algorithm setting groups of 2 m. Observations with higher values were considered low-quality. Hereafter, we refer to this filtering approach as ASG.

2.4.3. Additional Filters

A zero value of the “degrade flag” indicates non-degraded conditions. Non-zero degrade flag values indicate that the shot was taken during a degraded period of positioning and/or pointing information (i.e., degraded altitude or trajectory; Beck et al., 2021), and such footprints are often removed (Figure 1). In addition, we also evaluated the effect of the signal strength (i.e., power/coverage beams) and time of acquisition (i.e., day/night acquisitions represented by solar elevation; positive values: day, negative values: night) on terrain and canopy height retrievals. These parameters are also often considered for GEDI data filtering (Figure 1). In addition, terrain slope is well known for its negative effect on space-borne lidar observations (e.g., Chen, 2010; Liu et al., 2021; Moudrý et al., 2022; Quiros et al., 2021). We derived rasters of slope from ALS DTMs and calculated the mean slope within a GEDI 25 m diameter footprint.

2.4.4. Assessment of Geolocation Error

To test for the effect of geolocation error, following Quirós et al. (2021) and Kutchartt et al. (2022) we shifted the footprints by 10 and 5 m in eight different directions: 0°, 45°, 90°, 135°, 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315°, relative to the ISS orbit direction. The direction was determined from the progression of shot numbers in the GEDI data. This resulted in 17 possible positions (the original position plus 16 alternative positions). For each position, terrain and canopy height were extracted from DTM and CHM, respectively. The optimal footprint location was determined by selecting the position with the lowest error, defined as the smallest difference between *elev_lowestmode* and the terrain height derived from DTM.

2.5. GEDI Pre-Processing and Footprints Selection

We downloaded GEDI L2A version 2 data acquired between April 2019 and September 2022 using the Earthdata portal (accessed September 2022). The GEDI L2A elevation of the center of the lowest mode (*elev_lowestmode*) representing the terrain height is given as ellipsoidal height (above WGS84 ellipsoid). In contrast, the vertical datum of the ALS data is given as orthometric (Spain, California) or normal (New Zealand) heights, respectively. Therefore, to match the elevation heights of the lowest mode and the reference ALS data, we subtracted relevant reference surfaces from the GEDI L2A terrain height. We used the EGM08-REDNAP geoid model for Spain (<https://datos-geodesia.ign.es/geoide/>), Geoid12B for California (<https://geodesy.noaa.gov/>), and New Zealand Quasigeoid 2016 for New Zealand (<https://data.linz.govt.nz/layer/53447-nz-quasigeoid-2016-raster/>). In order to match the horizontal datum with ALS data, we projected the position of the footprints into the local coordinate system of each study area (Table 1). We limited our evaluation to two landcover categories (according to ESA world cover product): tree cover (hereafter forests) and grassland. This resulted in a total of 740,779; 695,023; and 645,306 footprints in Cantabria, Marlborough, and Trinity, respectively.

2.6. Assessment of GEDI Observations Filtering Success and Accuracy

We first concentrated on the accuracy of the GEDI terrain estimates. In the first step, we compared the use of two acquisition parameters (number of modes and sensitivity) for the identification of noise observations, which were

then removed before the next step. The second step was to identify low-quality observations, which were subsequently removed, using three different approaches (QF, TDX, ASG). Finally, the remaining observations were analyzed with respect to additional characteristics that might affect GEDI observations, such as the degrade flag, laser pulse energy, time of acquisition, and slope.

We defined the vertical error in GEDI terrain estimates as their deviation from the reference surface derived from the respective ALS lidar DTM. The vertical error in GEDI terrain estimates was evaluated on pairwise vertical differences between the elevation lowest mode (*elev_lowestmode*, i.e., the elevation estimated using the GEDI-indicated preferred algorithm setting group) of individual footprints and the lidar DTM. We used the mean elevation within a buffer with a 25 m diameter. The error distributions were summarized using two error metrics—specifically, the mean error (ME) and RMSE, represented as:

$$ME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (h_{GEDi} - h_{REFi})$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (h_{GEDi} - h_{REFi})^2}$$

where h_{GEDi} is the i th elevation from the GEDI L2A product, h_{REFi} is the corresponding “true” elevation from a lidar DTM, and n is the number of samples.

Our main goal was to study the effects of the acquisition and environmental characteristics on the quality of GEDI observations rather than to determine the absolute values of accuracy. We, therefore, focused on visualizing the distribution of vertical error using density plots and box plots because single-value metrics, such as ME and RMSE are a simplification and can be misleading. To investigate the effect of acquisition and environmental characteristics, we stratified the graphs and error metrics concerning the acquisition and environmental (i.e., landcover and slope) parameters (see Sections 2.4. and 2.5). In addition to removing inaccurate measurements, it is also important that the used approaches do not remove accurate measurements. Therefore, we selected high-quality observations, that is, GEDI footprints with the error in terrain estimate lower than 3 m, and evaluated the success of the noise filtering and low-quality data filtering criteria (Figure 3) in maintaining high-quality observations. We based the threshold for high-quality observations on the theoretical vertical accuracy of GEDI canopy height estimates, which is approximately 2–3 m (Hakkenberg, Tang, et al., 2023).

Finally, we calculated pairwise vertical differences between the maximum canopy height (RH98) of individual GEDI footprints and canopy height models (CHM) derived from ALS and assessed the effect of error in GEDI terrain height estimates, slope, number of modes, and sensitivity on the accuracy of canopy height estimates.

3. Results

3.1. Accuracy of Terrain Estimates

3.1.1. Noise Filtering (Number of Modes and Sensitivity)

The number of detected modes increased with increasing sensitivity and had a profound effect on the observed terrain accuracy (Figure 4). The best terrain accuracy was recorded for observations with one to four modes. Further increase in the number of modes tended to underestimate the terrain; this effect was more pronounced in grasslands than in forests (Figure 4).

In each area, the two criteria (number of detected modes >0 and sensitivity between 0.9 and 1) agreed in the identification of useable/noise observations in more than 85%. The number of detected modes criterion preserved more observations for the subsequent analysis than sensitivity (Figure 5). The sensitivity criterion tended to miss less than 1% of observations with zero detected modes. On the other hand, approximately 5% of the observations with at least one detected mode were removed due to the low sensitivity (i.e., sensitivity flag <0.9). However, many such observations could be useful (Figure 6a). Observations with one detected mode in grasslands provide accurate terrain estimates. On the other hand, in forests, such observations may represent vegetation canopy and overestimate terrain height (Figure 6a).

Figure 4. Density plots illustrate the distribution of elevation differences between GEDI (*elev_lowestmode*) and ALS DTM according to the number of modes classified by sensitivity and landcover type (grassland-top, forest-bottom). The number of detected modes increased with increasing sensitivity and had a profound effect on the observed terrain accuracy. Note the tendency of GEDI observations with a high number of modes in grasslands to considerably underestimate the terrain. In forests, this tendency is much lower. Observations with zero detected modes were clearly noise observations. The pattern was the same for all study areas; therefore, in this case, we merged them and the figure shows a combined result from all study areas.

We grouped the observations identified as noise according to landcover, time of acquisition (day/night), and beam strength to determine the characteristics most associated with the loss of signal (Table 2). The signal from the power beam was less often lost than that from the coverage beam (Table 2). Only 20% of power beam observations were identified as noise compared to approximately 30% of the coverage beam observations. The signal from the power beam showed higher sensitivity values than the coverage beam (Figure 6b). The landcover and time of acquisition (day or night) had no effect on beam sensitivity (Figure 6b) and observations removal (Table 2).

3.1.2. Low-Quality Data Filtering (QF, TDX, ASG)

In the previous section, we clearly showed that observations with zero detected modes or sensitivities between 0.1 and 0.9 were mostly noise; they were, therefore, removed and only the remaining observations (1,195,259) were used in all comparisons in the second-tier analysis presented in this section. As shown in Figure 7a, the error distributions for observations with low differences between ASGs were considerably narrower than those for

Figure 5. Venn diagram showing the percentage of observations filtered using the number of modes and sensitivity. Note that approximately 25%–46% of GEDI footprints in our study areas are noise observations and do not provide any useful information. Between 48.5% and 69.5% of GEDI footprints passed both criteria (number of modes ≥ 1 and sensitivity ≥ 0.9).

measurements with high differences between ASGs. Similarly, the difference from TDX lower than 50 m and, to some degree, also the difference from TDX lower than 100 m showed a narrow distribution of error symmetric around zero, while observations with differences from TDX higher than 100 m were erroneous in two out of the three study areas (Figure 7b). The density plots in Figure 7c illustrate the effect of the quality flag. A narrow distribution symmetric around zero was observed for the quality flag equal to one, while a multimodal distribution with high positive error was evident for the quality flag equal to zero. Note, however, that the quality flag equal to 0 may also include some accurate observations (Figure 7c).

Only 4%–25% of observations (depending on the study area) were identified as low-quality by all algorithms (QF = 1, TDX < 100 m, ASG < 2 m), which indicates low agreement among them. ASG was the most restrictive approach that removed most of the observations (75%–80%). The QF and TDX approaches, on the other hand, were less stringent and their combination resulted in preserving 70%–90% of all non-noise observations (see Figure S1). Combining ASG with TDX was, in terms of accuracy, the best approach (RMSEs ranging from 6.3 to 11.1 m), followed by the combination of all methods, in which case RMSEs ranging from 7.1 to 11.7 m were achieved (Figure 8). Combining QF with TDX yielded slightly lower accuracy (RMSEs ranging from 11.2 to 13.2 m); however, only 10%–30% of all observations were removed (compared to 75%–80% in the ASG + TDX approach). The use of only one of the conditions, no matter which one, performed poorly and led to the selection of observations with high RMSEs (Figure 8).

3.1.3. Success in Retaining High-Quality Observations

We evaluated the success of the noise filtering and low-quality data filtering criteria in preserving high-quality observations (i.e., with an absolute error of terrain estimates <3 m). Only 19.5%, 24.5%, and 30.8% of observations from the original unfiltered data set met the high-quality criteria in Cantabria, Marlborough, and Trinity, respectively. In noise filtering, the number of detected modes criterion was more successful in keeping high-quality observations than sensitivity. The Number of detected modes criterion led to the removal of less than 1% of high-quality observations. In comparison, sensitivity removed between 9% and 15% of high-quality

Figure 6. (a) Box plots showing the relationships between the elevation error of GEDI terrain, sensitivity, landcover (forests and grasslands), and number of modes (observations with zero detected modes were clearly noise observations, see Figure 4, and were not used in this plot). Note that observations with one detected mode, especially in grasslands, provide accurate terrain estimates even for sensitivity values lower than 0.9 (such observations are typically removed as noise). In forests, however, observations with one detected mode and low sensitivity may represent vegetation canopy and overestimate terrain height (e.g., in Marlborough). Note that in grasslands or forests of relatively low height and density (e.g., Cantabria) a combination of the sensitivity higher than 0.9 and a high number of detected modes can lead to considerable error in terrain estimates. (b) Box plots showing the relationships between sensitivity, beam strength, landcover, and time of acquisition. Note that strong beams have higher sensitivity than coverage beams.

Table 2
Percentage of GEDI Observations Identified as Noise in Forests and Grasslands With Respect to the Time of Acquisition and Beam Strength

	Forest		Grassland	
	Day	Night	Day	Night
Power beam	20.0	19.7	19.6	19.6
Coverage beam	31.0	29.3	33.2	27.7

observations. In the low-quality data filtering, ASG was the most restrictive approach, removing approx. 60%–65% of high-quality observations. The QF and TDX approaches, on the other hand, were less stringent and their combination resulted in the removal of less than 1% of high-quality observations (see Figure S1).

3.1.4. Additional Filters (Degrade Flag, Beam Strength, Time of Acquisition, Slope)

In the previous section, we showed that the combination of QF + TDX approaches led to the successful removal of low-quality observations while keeping most of the observations available for further analysis. Therefore, we removed low-quality observations using the QF and TDX approach, and only the remaining observations (991,932) were used in all comparisons in this section.

In both forests and grasslands, the accuracy of GEDI terrain estimates deteriorated with the increasing terrain slope (Figure 9a). In addition, GEDI tends to identify a higher number of modes with increasing slope (Figure 9b). Maneuvering or other ISS operations (stored in the *degrade_flag*) causing degraded positioning and/or pointing information also led to low accuracy of terrain observations. Importantly, it cannot be assumed that all problematic measurements caused by maneuvering would be removed by the low-quality filtering used in the previous section. In particular, degrade flag values 5, 50, and 85 were not removed by low-quality data filtering in our study areas (Figure 10). We did not find any effect of the time of acquisition (day or night) on GEDI terrain accuracy (Figure 10).

3.2. Accuracy of Canopy Height Estimates

3.2.1. Number of Modes and Sensitivity

In this section, we illustrate the effect of the number of detected modes and sensitivity on the quality of canopy height estimates in forests and grasslands (we used only observations with the number of detected modes higher than zero). The observed canopy height accuracy was strongly related to the number of detected modes. The density plots of height differences between GEDI RH98 and lidar-derived CHM (i.e., GEDI RH98 absolute vertical error) showed different patterns with respect to the number of detected modes, landcover, and study area (Figure 11). In Cantabria, the best accuracy of forest canopy height was achieved for observations with a relatively low number of detected modes (2–4 modes); in Marlborough, the best accuracy came with a slightly higher number (9–12 modes), and in Trinity, the highest number of modes (13–20 modes) performed best. This corresponds to the canopy height in the respective study areas—the canopy height in study areas where more modes provided better accuracy is higher (Figure 1). In grasslands, on the other hand, GEDI tended to overestimate the canopy height and the overestimation increased with the number of detected modes (Figure 11), which likely resulted from incorrect classification of noise modes below the terrain as actual terrain (Figure 4).

The sensitivity criterion (between 0.9 and 1.0) showed its importance for the removal of noise observations in forests where sensitivity values <0.9 led to an underestimation of canopy height (Figure 12a). In Trinity and, to some degree, also in Marlborough, canopy height was on average underestimated even for sensitivity values >0.9 (Figure 12b). In grasslands, however, observations with sensitivity values <0.9 had high accuracy and were still useable, except for Trinity (Figure 12a). Moreover, in grasslands, sensitivity values >0.9 led to an increase in error and overestimation of canopy height, particularly in Marlborough and Cantabria (Figure 12b).

3.2.2. Effect of the Terrain on the Accuracy of Canopy Height Estimates

The accuracy of terrain estimates (see Section 3.1) is crucial for estimates of canopy height. Therefore, we also demonstrate the role of accurate terrain observations in determining canopy height estimates. In this section, we used only observations with the number of detected modes higher than 0 and sensitivity between 0.9 and 1.0 (i.e., we removed noise observations). As expected, in forests, the underestimation of terrain elevation led to the overestimation of canopy height and vice versa. In grasslands, however, both overestimation and underestimation of the terrain led to the overestimation of canopy height (Figure 13a). The overestimation of canopy height

Figure 7. Density plots depicting the distribution of differences in terrain height (GEDI elevation–elevation derived from ALS DTM), in meters, according to: (a) the elevation difference between Algorithm setting groups; (b) the absolute difference between GEDI terrain elevation and TanDEM-X DEM; and (c) the quality flag (*quality_flag*).

increased with the increasing slope (Figure 13b). This is because GEDI tended to identify a higher number of modes with increasing slope (Figure 9b), which likely resulted in the detection of multiple modes incorrectly considered as vegetation and, therefore, resulting in an observed overestimation of canopy height (Figure 13b),

Figure 8. Venn diagrams of the performance of three approaches for filtering out low-quality data in the three study areas. The three approaches are: (QF) Quality flag equal to one; (TDX) absolute difference between the GEDI (*elev_lowestmode*) and elevation from TanDEM-X lower than 100 m; and (ASG) the range of ground elevations predicted by six algorithm setting groups is lower than 2 m. The values show performance metrics of individual or combined filtering approaches. We used the following performance metrics: Mean error and root mean square error. For more performance metrics see Figure S1.

particularly in grasslands (Figure 11). Observations with large terrain errors (>50 m) were an exception, not following these trends and causing large errors in canopy height observations (Figure 13a).

3.3. Geolocation Error

We showed that maneuvering or other ISS operations causing degraded positioning and/or pointing information led to low accuracy of terrain observations. Therefore, we removed observations with a degrade flag equal to 5, 50, and 85, and only the remaining observations (963,709) were used in all comparisons in this section.

We shifted footprints in eight directions by two different distances to determine the approximate direction and magnitude of the geolocational error and its effect on the accuracy of the terrain and canopy height estimates. The shift by 10 m led to improved accuracy in 70% of the footprints, shift by 5 m in another 26% (no improvement after the shift was observed in the remaining 4%, see Table 3). Neither direction was generally predominant, with the exception of Marlborough, where a 135° shift of footprints was the most common (Figure 14). The accuracy of GEDI terrain estimates improved with locational shifts. However, this did not lead to a corresponding improvement in vegetation height estimates (Table 3, Figure 15). In addition, the success in minimizing the geolocation error depended on the number of modes and landcover (Figure 15). In forests, minimizing the geolocation error led to a notable improvement in the accuracy of terrain estimates. In grasslands, on the other hand, we observed much lower improvement in the accuracy of footprints with many modes, suggesting that these are more severely affected by the measurement characteristics other than the geolocational error.

4. Discussion

In this study, we examined the effect of acquisition characteristics (such as number of detected modes, sensitivity, beam strength, solar background noise, slope) on the vertical accuracy of GEDI terrain (*elev_lowestmode*) and canopy (*RH98*) height estimates and determined their usability for identifying noise (e.g., when a beam could not reach the Earth's solid surface), and low-quality observations (e.g., when a return from canopy is identified as ground return). In this way, approximately 51.5%, 44.2%, and 30.5% of observations were identified as noise in the Cantabria, Marlborough, and Trinity regions, respectively (Figure 5). Additionally, 14.7%, 8.0%, and 6.0% of observations were categorized as low-quality in the same regions. Consequently, after the removal of noise and low-quality data, the retained data yielded percentages of 33.8%, 47.8%, and 63.5% for Cantabria, Marlborough, and Trinity, respectively.

Figure 9. (a) Boxplots showing the relationship between terrain accuracy, slope, and landcover. Note that the accuracy of GEDI terrain estimates decreases with increasing slope, which can be used as an additional filter if highly accurate data are needed. (b) Boxplots show the relationship between the number of modes, terrain slope, and landcover. Note that the number of detected modes considerably increases with terrain slope in both landcover types.

4.1. Number of Modes, Sensitivity, and Slope

Our results show that using a non-zero number of detected modes is a useful first filter to identify noise observations while keeping high-quality observations. In addition, the number of detected modes profoundly affected the observed terrain and canopy height accuracy. In forests, there was an association between the true (ALS-determined) canopy height and the optimum number of modes; for example, 9–12 modes provided the best results in Marlborough, which is characterized by tall vegetation, but only 2–4 modes in Cantabria where low forests predominate (Figure 11). In grasslands, there was a tendency to underestimate the terrain with an increasing number of modes, which, in turn, led to an overestimation of the canopy height (Figures 4 and 11). This problem was most evident on steep slopes. The number of modes increases with increasing slope (Figure 9b), suggesting that the waveform on steep slopes (or in a rugged terrain) takes a bimodal (or even multimodal) shape. One mode is reflected by the bottom of the slope, while the other by the top of the slope, with the latter being treated as vegetation. On slopes greater than 45°, we observed median underestimation of terrain (Figure 9) and corresponding overestimation of canopy height of up to 10 m (Figure 13b). This finding corresponds with prior studies that reported considerable effect of terrain slope and/or number of modes on GEDI terrain and canopy height estimates in both forested and non-forested landscapes (Quirós et al., 2021; Urbazaev et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022).

Filtering using the sensitivity criterion must be applied with caution and the character of the landcover (e.g., height and density of vegetation) must be taken into account. The sensitivity criterion (sensitivity between 0.9 and

Figure 10. Boxplots showing the accuracy of GEDI terrain estimates of power and coverage beams, also considering the degrade flag (a) and time of acquisition (b). Plots are after the removal of noise and low-quality observations.

Figure 11. Density plots depicting the distribution of canopy height differences between GEDI (RH98) and ALS-derived CHM according to the number of modes grouped by landcover type. The optimal number of modes in forests differs considerably with the study area. More modes provided better accuracy in the study areas with higher canopy height (e.g., Trinity). On the other hand, in Cantabria with relatively low forest canopy height, footprints with high numbers of modes provided clearly erroneous values. Note the tendency of GEDI observations to overestimate the canopy height in grasslands with the growing number of modes.

Figure 12. Box plots depicting the relationship between the error of GEDI canopy height estimates, landcover (forests and grasslands), beam strength, and sensitivity (a) from 0 to 1 and (b) only values higher than 0.9. Note the underestimation of forest canopy height for sensitivity values lower than 0.9. In dense forests (e.g., Marlborough, Trinity), sensitivity values even higher than 0.9 are needed to select high-accuracy observations. On the other hand, in grasslands, observations with high sensitivity may lead to the detection of multiple modes and, consequently, to the overestimation of canopy height. This is especially common on steep slopes (see also Figures 9 and 11).

1) showed its importance for the removal of noise observations in forests where sensitivity values lower than 0.9 lead to an underestimation of canopy height (Figure 12a). Such a threshold works well for forests of relatively low height and density, such as in Cantabria. However, in high and dense forests, such as Trinity and Marlborough (Figure 2), a higher sensitivity threshold, for example, 0.95, is needed, as also recommended by the GEDI user guide (Beck et al., 2021). In addition, it was recently shown by Fayad et al. (2022) that in densely vegetated areas, beams with high sensitivity (≥ 0.98) have a higher chance of reaching the ground. On the other hand, in grasslands, a high sensitivity criterion tended to remove useful observations (Figure 6). However, observations in grasslands are equally important as those from forested areas for successful modeling of canopy height at fine resolutions (e.g., Lang et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021; Schwartz et al., 2023). Filtering them out using the sensitivity or quality flag criteria (Figure 1; quality flag uses a sensitivity threshold of 0.9) results in a reduced number of samples for model fitting. Approximately 5% of observations in each study area were removed this way (Figure 5). Therefore, we recommend using different sensitivity values for different landcover types to avoid unwanted removal of accurate observations. Over landcover types with low or sparse vegetation, such as grasslands, we recommend using a sensitivity higher than 0.5 (Figure 12a; which is also used over the ocean; Beck et al., 2021) but lower than 0.9. Sensitivity greater than 0.9 resulted in an overestimation of canopy height in grasslands, especially on steep slopes, where high sensitivity led to the detection of multiple modes, causing an overestimation of canopy heights. Alternatively, this issue could be addressed by excluding observations in grassland areas, on steep slopes, and those with a high number of modes (e.g. higher than 5).

4.2. Best Filtering of Low-Quality Observations (QF, ASG, TDX)

Even if observations pass the first noise filter, they may still have low accuracy, which limits their use for further analysis. Indeed, our results show that only 20%–31% of observations had an absolute vertical error of terrain estimates < 3 m. However, the identification of low-quality observations is challenging, and studies use different approaches for low-quality data filtering (Figure 1). Only 4%–25% of observations were identified as low-quality

Figure 13. (a) Box plot showing the relationship between CHM accuracy and accuracy of terrain estimates. Note that in forests, an overestimation of terrain leads to the underestimation of canopy height and vice versa. (b) Box plot showing a relationship between the terrain slope and error in canopy height estimates. Note that the coverage and power beams are equally affected by the slope.

by all algorithms, which indicates low agreement among them (Figure 8). However, none of the approaches is superior. Using only one of the approaches may lead to the selection of observations with high RMSEs (Figure 8); therefore, we recommend combining at least two approaches. ASG was the most restrictive approach, and we do not recommend using it, as it removes a large number of high-quality observations (Figure 8). On the other hand, the combination of QF and TDX approaches was less stringent, kept most of the high-quality observations, and achieved similar accuracies in terms of RMSE as when ASG was used. Therefore, the combination of these two approaches could be recommended, especially when it is important to minimize the reduction of the number of observations.

Removing observations with high absolute differences from global DEMs is a common approach (Figure 1). In our study areas, the difference between TanDEM-X DEM and GEDI terrain observations higher than 100 m indicated mostly erroneous measurements (Figure 7). The absolute vertical accuracy of global DEMs, such as

Table 3
Frequency of Shifts, Terrain and Canopy Height Accuracy Measures Before and After Shifting

	Frequency of shifts (%)			Terrain				Canopy			
				ME (m)		RMSE (m)		ME (m)		RMSE (m)	
	0 m	5 m	10 m	Original	Shifted	Original	Shifted	Original	Shifted	Original	Shifted
Cantabria	3.8	27.9	68.3	-2.0	-0.5	10.9	9.0	5.5	7.2	10.7	11.4
Marlborough	3.2	24.2	72.6	0.2	0.5	12.7	9.4	0.9	1.3	8.3	8.2
Trinity	3.5	25.9	70.6	-2.5	-0.9	11.3	8.3	-7.3	-6.6	13.8	13.3

Figure 14. Percentage of shifts of GEDI footprints with respect to shift magnitude and direction.

TanDEM-X, depends on terrain characteristics and canopy height and, hence, considerably differs among landcover types (Gdulová et al., 2020; Hawker et al., 2019). Therefore, care must be taken when selecting the threshold, and the landcover type and forest height should be considered. Low absolute difference thresholds (e.g., 50 m) can lead to removing useful observations (Urbazaev et al., 2022). In forests, such as in our study areas, we recommend a 100 m threshold; in grasslands, it is reasonable to use a 50 m threshold. Accurate terrain models from ALS data are available in the United States, Australia, New Zealand, and many countries in Europe (e.g., Moudrý et al., 2023; Stoker & Miller, 2022). In this case, using such models in combination with a more stringent threshold is more appropriate for the selection of accurate GEDI observations.

4.3. Degrade Flag, Beam Type, and Time of Acquisition

Our results show that the degrade flag is an important parameter to consider when filtering GEDI observations, as degraded observations may not be removed by noise or low-quality filters. Degrade flags 5, 50, and 85 (see Beck et al., 2021 for the explanation of these values) were particularly problematic in our study areas. On the other hand, using the degrade flag considerably lowered the number of available observations. We observed an additional 19.5% decrease in number of observations. These results correspond with the recent study by Urbazaev et al. (2022), who showed that applying the GEDI degrade flag reduced the number of GEDI observations by more than 20%. Considering individual classes of the degrade flag and removing only classes that cause large errors (e.g., by comparing to TanDEM-X DEM) might minimize losses.

The time of acquisition did not considerably affect the quality of observations in our study areas (Figure 10). Similarly, Liu et al. (2021) concluded that the accuracy of the GEDI data acquired during the day and at night is almost identical, but some studies suggested otherwise (Adam et al., 2020). The beam type did not affect the quality of retrieved terrain and canopy height observations, either (Figures 9 and 12), but the signal from the power beam was less often lost than that from the coverage beam (Table 2). Other studies, such as Liu et al. (2021) over multiple sites in the United States and, more recently, Rodda et al. (2023) in a tropical dry forest in India, however, typically reported that power beams were more accurate than coverage beams. Such differences might be, for example, related to forest types evaluated in individual studies. In addition, beam strength is an input for calculating sensitivity; therefore, if a sensitivity criterion is applied, coverage beams of potentially low accuracy are removed in that step. We recommend using both power and coverage beams in temperate forests and grasslands, regardless of whether they were acquired during the day or night.

Figure 15. Box plots illustrating the height differences between GEDI and ALS reference data for terrain (a) and canopy (b) height estimates before (original) and after (shifted) correction for geolocation error, categorized by the number of modes and landcover type.

4.4. Mitigation of Geolocation Error

Our results show that locational shifts improved the accuracy of GEDI terrain estimates. All directions of data shifts were evenly presented, and none of them dominated (Figure 14). Although prior studies highlighted systematic shifts in locations of the first release of GEDI footprints (Kutchartt et al., 2022; Quirós et al., 2021), our results rather correspond to the more recent findings indicating that the second release of GEDI data, used in this study, achieved improved geolocation accuracy (Tang et al., 2023). However, the ability to mitigate geolocation error using high-resolution DTM decreased with the increasing number of detected modes (Figure 15), which was consistent with the observation that the same issue was reported for slope (Quirós et al., 2021) and that the number of detected modes increased with increasing slope (Figure 9b). This suggests that geolocational error should be

considered only together with other characteristics, such as slope or the number of modes, the impact of which on the GEDI accuracy can be much higher than that of the geolocation error itself. Furthermore, the improvement in the accuracy of terrain height estimates did not lead to a corresponding improvement in vegetation height estimates (Table 3). Similar results were reported by other studies (Schleich et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2023). It is therefore possible that mitigating geolocation error using high-resolution DTM is insufficient and that approaches based on simulated waveforms are more appropriate (e.g., Roy et al., 2021).

4.5. Limitations & Future Research

Here, we only tested filtering in temperate forests and grasslands. We do show that the filtering may need to be adjusted depending on the landcover types. Therefore, it would be important to also test filtering approaches across other biomes and landcover types. In tropical forests, for example, the optimal filtering may be different from temperate forests, as previously shown, for example, by Fayad et al. (2022) and Lahssini et al. (2022). For example, in tropical forests, it might be reasonable to use only power beams and sensitivity higher than 0.98 (e.g., Ngo et al., 2023; Oliveira et al., 2023). Future research could focus on this knowledge gap to provide a more comprehensive overview of GEDI data filtering across all biomes (Figure 1). In addition, we considered only terrain and canopy height observations, but we did not look at the estimates of the vertical canopy structure in between that top canopy height and terrain. Future research could focus on the retrieval of such metrics as well, given that those are often used to assess forests. Here, we specifically focused on the filtering of the GEDI waveforms and we chose a value of absolute canopy height as the representative of “high-quality observations”, we did not propagate errors of canopy height through to subsequent applications. This, and the effect of erroneous GEDI measurements on subsequent data applications (e.g., Marselis et al., 2019, 2022) and products such as Foliage height diversity index (Hirschmugl et al., 2023), Leaf area index (Wang et al., 2023), or above ground biomass (Dorado-Roda et al., 2021), could be studied in the future to further establish what a high-quality observation entails.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we evaluated the most effective ways of identifying noise and low-quality observations from GEDI, while keeping high-quality observations among the non-noise waveforms. We conclude that to identify noise observations in temperate forests and grasslands, it is best to filter by the ‘number of modes’ and remove all observations with less than 1 mode. The “sensitivity” metric must be considered together with landcover. The recommended sensitivity threshold of 0.9 was sufficient in the forests of Cantabria, but higher values were required in the forests of Marlborough and Trinity. On the other hand, in areas with sparse tall vegetation, such as grasslands or low-density forests, sensitivity down to 0.5 can be considered. Importantly, sensitivity higher than 0.9 typically overestimates canopy height in grasslands. This can be avoided by removing observations with a high number of modes (e.g. higher than 5) in grasslands. We found that to filter out the low-quality observations (following the noise removal in the previous step), the combination of the quality flag (QF) and difference from TanDEM-X DEM was the most effective in terms of trade-off between removing incorrect observations and retaining as many high-quality observations as possible. Additional filters that are important to pay attention to include the degrade flag and the terrain slope. Beam type and time of acquisition (day/night) did not improve the retention of high-quality observations and are, therefore, not seen as essential in temperate forests and grasslands.

Data Availability Statement

The evaluated GEDI L2A Elevation and Height Metrics Data are provided free of charge (Dubayah, Hofton, et al., 2021). The original airborne laser scanning data used for the validation are sourced from the LINZ Data Service and OpenTopography, and licensed for reuse under the CC BY 4.0 license (LINZ, 2023); Spanish National Geographic Institute (SNGI, 2023); and U.S. Geological Survey (USGS, 2023).

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